

The Quality of Library Facilities and Services of St. Paul University Philippines Junior High School Department: From the Lens of the University's Stakeholders

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ABSTRACT : This study sought to assess the quality of library facilities and services of the Junior High School Department of St. Paul University Philippines during the Academic Year 2018 - 2019. Furthermore, the study elicited the participants' recommendations to further improve the library services and facilities of the department. The descriptive research design was utilized in this study and involved as research participants Grade 7, Grade 8, Grade 9 and Grade 10 students at St. Paul University Philippines. The questionnaire was utilized as the primary data gathering tool. The data collected were tabulated, analyzed, interpreted, and summarized using frequency count, percentage, mean and One-Way Analysis of Variance. The participants rated the SPUP Junior High School Department's library collections and resources as "good" while its library set-up and atmosphere, library staff and accessibility of library services as "very good". The participants recommended for better ventilation inside the library as well as the acquisition of more computer terminals with internet access, more air conditioning units installed and faster internet speed in the library.

KEYWORDS -accessibility of services, collections and resources, library staff, library set-up and atmosphere

I. INTRODUCTION

The library facility and services is one of the most important services that any educational institution could offer and provide its clients. The teaching and learning processes are highly dependent on the quality and adequacy of the library facilities and services. It greatly affects the quality of education that any school could offer its students and teachers. Considering then its crucial importance, schools need to regularly assess their library services and facilities to determine whether they indeed are providing the learning and teaching needs of their academic community. Integrating the results of assessment activities will bring about an improvement of student learning and the provision of better library and other support services on campus [1].

Normally, a lot of librarians have relied more on instincts and experience rather than data and metrics generated from library assessments to make their decisions. On the other hand, a library can develop a "culture of assessment" in which decisions are based on an analysis of local data. Librarians need to consider the results of research in other libraries and focus on facts. A culture of assessment has also been called a "culture of curiosity or a 'culture of evidence'. A culture of assessment-based library focuses on planning and delivering services that maximize the anticipated outcomes and impacts for its customers and stakeholders. The library's staff members must have a clear understanding of what customers expect and value. Thus, the collection and analysis of data, even data collected in an ad hoc or unsystematic manner, can be useful in more accurately

defining a problem and in exposing activities or processes that may require further study and analysis, as well as in observing the progress that is being made to achieve specific goals and objectives [1]. As Jamene Brooks-Kieffer in her article titled “Yielding to Persuasion: Library Data’s Hazardous Surfaces” published in “Library Data: Empowering Practice and Persuasion” pointed that any assessment data is not meaningful to the organization until it is allowed to inform some action [2]. There is then a necessity for library staff and library heads to continuously see to it that facilities and services need to be upgraded and enhanced.

St. Paul University Philippines, being a school renowned for its uncompromising quest for quality and excellence and its Basic Education Unit’s (BEU) status as a Level 4 PAASCU accredited, the University, specifically the BEU need to regularly conduct assessment of its facilities and services, the library included in consonance to its mission of providing customer delight and satisfaction and of providing quality education for its stakeholders, thus, this study.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

This study titled “The Quality of Library Facilities and Services of St. Paul University Philippines Junior High School Department: From the Lens of the University’s Stakeholders” sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the participants in terms of grade level?
2. What is the participants’ assessment of the quality of library facilities and services of St. Paul University Philippines Junior High School Department when they are grouped according to grade level in terms of:
 - 2.1 library set-up and atmosphere;
 - 2.2 library collections and resources;
 - 2.3 library staff; and
 - 2.4 accessibility of services?
3. Is there a significant difference in the participants’ assessment of the quality of library facilities and services of St. Paul University Philippines Junior High School Department when they are grouped according to grade level?
4. What are the participants’ suggestions to further improve the quality of library facilities and services of St. Paul University Philippines Junior High School Department?

II. METHODS

2.1 Research Design

The research design that was used in the study is the descriptive research design as it sought to assess the quality of library facilities and services of St. Paul University Philippines Junior High School Department.

2.2 Research Participants

The research participants of the study consisted of randomly selected Grade 7 to Grade 10 students of St. Paul University Philippines enrolled during the school year 2018 – 2019 since they are the ones directly utilizing the library facilities and are the recipients of the services of the library personnel.

2.3 Data Gathering Tools

The researchers made use of the following instrument and methods in gathering the needed data for the study.

Questionnaire. This was utilized as tool for the participants to assess the quality of the library facilities as well as the quality of services provided to them by the library personnel. The survey questionnaire underwent content-validation by five (5) experts and the obtained content validity index is 0.95 which means that the instrument is valid and indeed measures what it intends to measure.

Interview Guide. This tool enabled the researchers to get additional data and information on the participants' suggestions to further improve the quality of library facilities and services of St. Paul University Philippines Junior High School Department.

2.4 Data Gathering Procedure

Before gathering and collecting data, the researcher sought the proper authorization and permission from the Knowledge Information Resource Network (KIRN) Director to conduct the study. The researcher obtained the needed items or pieces of information from her readings of related literature and used them for the development of the assessment tool. The researcher sought the assistance of a research expert during the course of the development of the tool to ensure its content and face validity.

The researcher administered the assessment tool to some selected grade 7, 8, 9 and 10 students in the SPUP Basic Education Unit and collated the retrieved tool using Microsoft Excel. The collated data were later subjected to statistical treatment using SPSS Version 17 and the statistical outputs were analyzed and interpreted.

2.5 Data Analysis

The data collected were tabulated, analyzed, interpreted, and summarized using descriptive statistics. Descriptive statistics, like frequency counts, percentage, mean and One-Way Analysis of Variance were used to interpret the gathered data to answer the study's problem statement.

Frequency and Percentage. This was used to describe the profile of the participants in terms of their grade level.

Mean. This was used to describe the weighted mean response of the participants in terms of their assessment as to the quality of the library facilities as well as the quality of services provided to them by the library personnel. To interpret the weighted mean assessment responses of the participants, the following mean range descriptions are used.

Mean Range	Qualitative Description
3.26 – 4.00	Very Good
2.51 – 3.25	Good
1.76 – 2.50	Poor
1.00 – 1.75	Very Poor

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Profile of Participants

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the participants grouped in terms of grade level.

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Participants Grouped in Terms of Grade Level

Grade Level	Frequency	Percentage
Grade 7	50	25.00
Grade 8	50	25.00
Grade 9	50	25.00
Grade 10	50	25.00
Total	200	100.00

Table 1 shows that the participants of this research are equally distributed across the four grade levels in the Junior High School Department, each consisting of one fourth or twenty five percent (25%) of the total sample size of 200 students.

3.2. Participants' Assessment of the Quality of Library Facilities and Services of St. Paul University Philippines Junior High School Department

3.2.1. Library Setup and Atmosphere

Table 2. Mean Distribution of the Participants' Assessment of the Quality of Library Facilities and Services of St. Paul University Philippines Junior High School Department in terms of Library Setup and Atmosphere

Statement	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. The library is a conducive place to study and do research work	3.57	Very Good
2. The library is well ventilated.	3.23	Good
3. The library is well lighted.	3.31	Very Good
4. The library is well maintained in terms of cleanliness and orderliness.	3.45	Very Good
5. The library rules and regulations are consistently observed and implemented.	3.28	Very Good
6. The library setup is appropriate and user friendly.	3.37	Very Good
7. The library ambience is generally peaceful and conducive for study and research.	3.39	Very Good
8. The library is spacious enough to accommodate the present number of students, faculty, and other clients.	3.32	Very Good
Category Mean	3.37	Very Good

The data in Table 2 shows that the student participants assessed the library facilities and services of the Junior High School Department as "Very Good" in terms of its conduciveness, lighting, cleanliness and orderliness, observance and implementation of library rules and regulations, its physical set-up, ambience and expanse of space. Only one area was adjudged as good and this is concerning the library's ventilation. The library's ventilation condition was also brought out during the researcher's casual or informal interview and observation with some of the Junior High School students. The interviewed students verbalized their comment that the number of air conditioning units inside the library is not sufficient to provide the needed ventilation for the library users.

Generally, in a school setting, air ventilation is of primordial importance as it greatly affects the quality of teaching and learning [3],[4]. Bakó-Biró, et. al [4] found in their research that performance tasks performed by their more than 200 pupil participants showed significantly faster and more accurate responses for Choice Reaction (by 2.2%), Colour Word Vigilance (by 2.7%), Picture Memory (by 8%) and Word Recognition (by 15%) at the higher ventilation rates compared with the low ventilation conditions[5]. Their study provided

strong evidence that low ventilation rates in classrooms significantly reduce learners' attention and vigilance, and negatively affect memory and concentration. The physical environment therefore affects teaching and learning.

3.2.2. Library Collections and Resources

Table 3. Mean Distribution of the Participants' Assessment of the Quality of Library Facilities and Services of St. Paul University Philippines Junior High School Department in terms of Library Collections and Resources

Statement	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. The library has many collections of print and non-print resources.	3.36	Very Good
2. The print resources that include Textbooks, Reference books (Dictionaries, Almanac, Encyclopedias, and Book of Facts, etc.) are adequate.	3.49	Very Good
3. The non-print library resources like ebooks, ejournals, etc. are updated and adequate.	3.18	Good
4. I know how to use these resources because it was discussed during the orientation.	3.17	Good
5. I find it easy to use/ browse these print resources.	3.33	Very Good
6. Books and other library resources are easy to find and access.	3.24	Good
7. The library provides enough online resources (computer and internet access) to help me complete my assignments and research work.	3.21	Good
8. The internet access in the library is fast and reliable.	2.98	Good
9. The print resources of the library are very useful especially when I am researching.	3.20	Good
10. The print resources of the library are very reliable and accurate (edited and corrected before getting published)	3.25	Good
11. The print resources of the library are regularly updated.	3.11	Good
12. The print resources of the library provide me with adequate information where I can have options to choose from.	3.21	Good
Category Mean	3.23	Good

The participants' evaluation of the Junior High School's library collections and resources is generally assessed as "good". Three aspects however were assessed as "very good" which involve the library's varied collections of print and non-print resources and the easy use/ browsing of the printed resources. On the other hand, the following areas were only rated by the participants as "good": the updatedness and adequacy of non-print materials such as ebooks and e-journals, the discussion of the use of library materials during student orientation, easy access of books and other library resources, provision of online resources for the making of assignments and research projects, the speed and reliability of the use of the internet inside the library, the usefulness, reliability and accuracy of the print resources as well as its regular updating and the provision of adequate information to the students so students will be able to make better choices of print resources to use.

To really entice students as well as teachers to make regular use of library information products and services is for library managers is to continuously update and enrich their library collections as this affects the teacher and learners' frequency of library use. Popoola [6] in her study found that 100 (25%), 90 (33.5%) and 210(52.5%) of her research participants most frequently, occasionally and rarely used their library information products and services, respectively. From her respondents who were fully aware but occasionally used it claimed that their libraries lacked current materials and good customer relations. Popoola [6] then stressed the need for library management to constantly update their collections. Continuously updating library holdings results to improved customer relations and services ensuring that library materials and services are relevant to the needs of the faculty, staff as well as students.

3.2.3. Library Collections and Resources

Table 4. Mean Distribution of the Participants' Assessment of the Quality of Library Facilities and Services of St. Paul University Philippines Junior High School Department in terms of Library Staff

Statement	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. The library staff is generally approachable and helpful.	3.54	Very Good
2. The library staff took time to orient the students, faculty and other clients on how to use the library resources and facilities.	3.37	Very Good
3. The library staff responds clearly and accurately to client inquiries.	3.49	Very Good
4. The library staff is generally courteous to their student, faculty and other clients.	3.38	Very Good
5. The library staff is accommodating and service oriented.	3.43	Very Good
6. The library staff is knowledgeable of the nature of their work.	3.52	Very Good
7. The library staff willingly assists their clients in their library needs and concerns.	3.44	Very Good
Category Mean	3.31	Very Good

The data in Table 4 shows that all items related to the evaluation of the staff members of the library were assessed as “very good”. The participants generally assessed the library staff as approachable and helpful, accommodating, courteous, service-oriented and knowledgeable. These qualities are indeed deemed important for all librarians to possess as their personal attributes and behavior towards their clients greatly affect their frequency of library visit and use. In the study of Younger [7] titled “An analysis of skills and qualities required by LIS employers 2004-2005” found that communication and interpersonal skills are among the top skills required from a librarian. The study also highlighted the skills that improve relations with customer.

The most important quality of a librarian is social in nature. They must have the people skills necessary to provide good customer service [8]. In addition, the study of Balog, et. al. [9], presented that the most important feature of a librarian according to their respondents' opinions include the librarian's know-how (59.1 %) followed by education (16.8 %) and kindness (11.5 %).

3.2.4. Library Accessibility of Services

Table 5. Mean Distribution of the Participants' Assessment of the Quality of Library Facilities and Services of St. Paul University Philippines Junior High School Department in terms of Library Accessibility of Services

Statement	Overall Mean	Qualitative Description
1. The resources of the library are easy to locate/find among the shelves and sections of the library.	3.33	Very Good
2. The resources of the library provide me the information I need accurately.	3.29	Very Good
3. The availability of backup copies of print resources in the library enables me to have access of the books that are already checked out.	3.34	Very Good
4. The library is open from 7:30 AM to 5 PM.	3.32	Very Good
5. There is always a library staff to attend to clients' needs and concerns the whole day.	3.31	Very Good
Category Mean	3.32	Very Good

The data in Table 5 show that all items concerning the SPUP Junior High School library's accessibility of services were rated by the participants as “very good”. These include easy location of library resources, provision of accurate information, the availability of backup copies of print resources, extent of duration of the opening of the library and the availability of library staff to attend to clients' needs and concerns.

3.3. Test of Significant Difference in the Participants' Assessment of the Quality of Library Facilities and Services of St. Paul University Philippines Junior High School Department when they are Grouped According to Grade Level

Table 6. One-Way Analysis of Variance Test of Significant Difference in the Participants' Assessment of the Quality of Library Facilities and Services of St. Paul University Philippines Junior High School Department when they are Grouped According to Grade Level

Area of Assessment	Grade Level	Mean	Standard Deviation	Computed F-Ratio	P-value
Library Setup and Atmosphere	Grade 7	3.44	0.37633	2.417	0.068
	Grade 8	3.42	0.33466		
	Grade 9	3.25	0.43021		
	Grade 10	3.34	0.43444		
Library Collections and Resources	Grade 7	3.33	0.33393	4.554	0.004*
	Grade 8	3.33	0.31580		
	Grade 9	3.07	0.45050		
	Grade 10	3.18	0.52361		
Library Staff	Grade 7	3.42	0.78480	2.275	0.081
	Grade 8	3.36	0.59796		
	Grade 9	3.34	0.59281		
	Grade 10	3.10	0.64681		
Accessibility of Services	Grade 7	3.36	0.54361	1.482	0.221
	Grade 8	3.39	0.37358		
	Grade 9	3.21	0.43408		
	Grade 10	3.30	0.46989		

*Significant at 0.01 level

Inferential tests were done to determine whether significant differences exist in the assessment of the participants when they are grouped according to grade level and the One-Way Analysis of Variance results are presented in Table 6. It can be noted based on the said table that generally there is no significant difference in the assessment of the participants on the quality of library facilities and services of St. Paul University Philippines Junior High School Department in terms of library set-up and atmosphere, library staff and accessibility of services when they are grouped according to grade level. It implies that the assessment of the four grade levels of students generally have the same “very good” rating on the said areas of assessment. However, in the area of library collections and resources, the assessments of grades 7 and 8 are significantly higher compared to the assessments of grades 9 and 10.

3.4. Participants' Recommendations to Further Improve the Quality of Library Facilities and Services of St. Paul University Philippines Junior High School Department

The participants of the study recommended the following to further improve the quality of library facilities and services of St. Paul University Philippines Junior High School Department:

- Provision of more computer terminals with internet access for students to conduct their research activities.
- Installation of more air conditioning units to provide the students with better ventilation inside the library.
- Increasing the internet speed of the internet facilities and equipment inside the library.

IV. CONCLUSION

The regular conduct of assessment to ascertain the quality of library facilities and services that are provided by St. Paul University Philippines particularly the Basic Education Unit to its students is a profound manifestation of the University's strong commitment to excellence and quality. The provision of quality library facilities and services to students is a crucial factor in ensuring better and more conducive environment for students' learning thus resulting to improved academic performance and greater extent of student satisfaction and delight as clients of the University. Students' assessment normally provides learning institutions with valid

and reliable feedback where institutions can use as basis for continual improvement initiatives as well as for decision making.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and the conclusions formulated, the researchers recommend the following:

1. The focal person in-charge of overseeing the operations of the library facility being studied may strongly recommend for additional purchase of non-print library resources like ebooks, ejournals to beef up its library collections and resources.
2. The internet access in the library must be upgraded to ensure that its use by the students is fast and reliable.
3. The SPUP administration may look into improving the ventilation condition of the Junior High School library.
4. The SPUP administration may consider installing more computer terminals inside the library where students can have online access to non-print resources to motivate them to do investigatory and research projects.

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